

A hybrid PZT-FBG sensing based damage detection

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ABSTRACT

In this paper authors investigated elastic guided wave-based damage localisation in thin panel made out of isotropic material. Elastic waves excitation is based on piezoelectric transducer. Wave sensing is based on fiber Bragg gratings (FBG) strain sensors and piezoelectric sensors. Piezoelectric transducers are very popular in applications related to elastic wave generation and sensing. The FBG strain sensors utilized in the past for quasi static or quasi-static strain sensing are more and more utilized in field of elastic wave sensing. In the case of FBG sensors the edge filtering method is utilized. In this purpose tunable laser source is used. Received optical signal is converted to the voltage signal based on photodetector. Attention in this research was focused on dual sensing using FBGs. For this purpose pair of FBG sensors located on the top and bottom surface is utilized. Damage localisation is based on delay-and-sum algorithm. In this paper experimental results are presented.

Keywords: guided waves, damage localization, piezoceramic transducer, fibre optic FBG sensors

1. INTRODUCTION

The state of the structures needs to be periodically or continually assessed. This allows to prevent catastrophic failures caused by damage initiation. For this purpose, non-destructive testing (NDE) in periodic assessment or Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) in continuous approach are utilized. The very promising SHM technique is one based on elastic guided waves (GW) propagation phenomenon. The most popular in guided waves-based SHM are transducers based on piezoelectric material. They are called PZT due to utilized piezoelectric material (lead zirconate titanate) or piezo wafers [1]. These transducers can be utilized as actuators or sensors. The network of PZTs is based on connections realized by electrical wires and due to this fact sensing process is prone to electromagnetic interferences (EMI). Due to high level of excitation signal driving the PZT actuators and its capacitive character the crosstalk is observed in elastic wave generation and sensing equipment.

To overcome the EMI related problem during the elastic wave sensing more and more popular are fiber optic strain sensors based on Bragg Grating (FBG). The signals in this approach are transmitted through the optical waveguides (fibre optic). The main advantages of FBGs are small diameters, elasticity allowing the integration with curved shape, possibility of embedding in composite structures, and multiplexing capability (many sensors in one wire). However they are passive devices working as sensors which is the main drawback.

Due to the mentioned features, from certain period of time they are gladly utilized in studies related to SHM sensing. In the case of the FBG-based SHM, the process of elastic wave generation is conducted using piezoelectric transducers (actuators). In the literature, such an approach was utilized for the plates [2], railways tracks [3], rotorcraft structures [4] and aircraft fuselage [5] assessment. In the case of FBG-based elastic wave sensing edge filtration method [6],[7] and passive diffuse noise cross-correlation technique extracting the coherent guided waves propagating between two sensors

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[5] are utilized. There are different methods of coupling the FBG with the structure like: surface-mounted, cantilever structure, remote sensing, mobile sensor or piezo ring structure [7].

The authors of this paper present preliminary results of hybrid PZT-FBG elastic wave sensing from the point of view of the elastic wave-based damage localisation. In this research pair of sensors (dual sensing) located at the top and bottom surfaces of panel were investigated. Authors investigated the artificial damage in the form of additional mass.

2. MEASUREMENT SETUP

The investigated specimen was the in the form of square aluminum panel with dimensions: 1000 mm × 1000 mm × 1 mm (Figure 1). Elastic wave excitation was realized using a piezoceramic transducer working as actuator (PZT A). The actuator was located in the middle of the panel according to Figure 1. The process of elastic wave sensing was conducted based on a pair of piezoelectric sensors (PZT S - Figure 1) and FBG sensors (FBG - Figure 1). All piezoelectric transducers were in the form of a disc with a diameter of 10 mm and thickness 0.5 mm made out of NCE51 material. The FBG have the grating length 10 mm. In the case of each sensor type, they were located on the top and bottom surfaces of the panel. The distance between the sensors and the wave actuation point was 250 mm. Artificial damage was investigated in this research. It was simulated by additional mass by using a pair of magnets on the top and bottom sides of specimen. There were four locations of magnet pairs investigated M1 - M4 shown in Figure 1. It need to be underlined that in the preliminary research that results are presented in this paper, only magnets M1 and M4 and wave sensing based on FBG were investigated.

Figure 1. Investigated specimen

The measurement set-up consisted of signal generator (PXIe-5413), piezoelectric signal amplifier, data acquisition card (PXIe-5105 PXI), tunable laser (APEX, wavelength 1526 nm to 1567 nm), optical signal circulator, photodetectors, PZT transducers, and FBG sensors.

In the case of FBG-based elastic wave sensing, the edge filtering method was utilized [7]. In this approach tunable laser is tuned to the FBG's reflectivity slope. The middle portion of the reflectivity curve is linear and has a very steep slope. As a result, a little shift in the reflectivity spectrum causes a large change in the optical power sensed by the photodetector. The amplification increases the FBG sensors' sensitivity to elastic waves. The FBG connections are made through a three port circulator. The first port is connected to the laser source, the second to FBG and the third to the amplified photodetector. The photodetector is then connected to the data acquisition card. The PZT sensors are connected directly to an data acquisition card.

The excitation signal was in the form of five cycles of sine modulated by the Hann window applied to the piezoelectric actuator. The carrier frequency of excitation was equal to 150 kHz.

3. METHOD AND RESULTS

In order to localise the damage, the delay-and-sum algorithm was employed that assigns to a point P at the inspected surface a numerical value – the squared windowed time signal W :

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^N W_i^2 \quad (1)$$

The length of the window (N) is the length of the excitation signal, while the starting point $i=1$ of the window corresponds to time needed to wave travel from the piezoelectric actuator that excites the wave, through the inspected point P , to the sensing point (FBG). In this particular study the focus was put on S_0 wave, so its velocity was taken for time calculations. In this specific case the sensing point is chosen at the middle of the FBG sensor. The pair of FBG sensors was used for damage localisation.

Firstly, the top FBG sensors was used for referential state showing indication of waves reflecting from the edges (Figure 2a). After placing the mass M1 simulating damage off-line of the sensors, the top FBG sensor showed no indication of the mass (Figure 2b). However the bottom FBG sensor gave clear indication of it (Figure 2b). Taking together both signals, from top and bottom sensor, the mass was successfully indicated as shown in Figure 2d).

Figure 2. Results of localization for off-line placed mass

The second damage case (named M4) includes the mass placed in-line of the sensors. Both top Figure 3a) and bottom (Figure 3b) FBG sensors indicated the presence of damage, as well as the sum of both signals (Figure 3c).

Figure 3. Results of localization for in-line placed mass

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study showed that the FBG sensors can effectively sense high frequency signals corresponding to the propagating elastic waves. Looking at the symmetric mode (S0) it was shown that the presence of discontinuity (mass) on the sample surface can be indicated. The placement of two sensors at one location allows for more robust localization, since if only one sensor is sensitive to damage signal still the location can be successfully pinpointed.

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